

ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL STATEMENT AND INVESTMENT DECISION: A STUDY OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS LISTED IN THE NIGERIAN EXCHANGE GROUP

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ABSTRACT:

This study examined the financial statements and investment decisions of listed deposit money banks on the Nigerian Exchange Group. Its specific objectives included analyzing the influence of earnings per share (EPS), dividend per share (DPS), and profit for the year on return on equity (ROE) within these banks. Utilizing an ex-post facto research design, the study primarily relied on secondary data gathered from the annual reports and financial statements of UBA, Zenith Bank, and Access Bank Plc over an eleven-year period from 2012 to 2022. This timeframe is particularly relevant as it encompasses significant economic fluctuations and regulatory changes that could impact the banking sector in Nigeria. Employing panel data regression analysis with E-Views 10, the study utilized multiple regressions to evaluate the combined effects of the independent variables on ROE. The findings indicated mixed results: EPS did not have a statistically significant impact on ROE ($p = 0.2201$), while DPS had a significant influence ($p = 0.0288$). Profit for the year was marginally insignificant at the 5% level ($p = 0.0502$). Based on these results, the study recommends that the management of listed banks in Nigeria prioritize dividends per share, as it has a significant impact on shareholder returns. While earnings per share may not show a direct effect, banks should still focus on improving overall profitability through cost reduction, revenue diversification, and operational efficiency, as these could indirectly enhance ROE.

Keywords: *financial statement, Return on equity, raw material consumable, staff cost, return on assets*

INTRODUCTION

In every business they prepare statement of profit and loss or income statement, to ascertain the net result of the business. Financial working whether it has earned some income or profit or instead incurred loss. It also prepares statement of financial position, also known as balance sheet, to find out the business position. Statement of financial position and statement of profit or loss are all under financial statement, but profit and loss retained earnings statement. According to Chris (2022) financial statement as written record that convert the business activity, and the financial performance of the company. Financial statement are often audited by government agencies, accounting firms, accountant to ensure accuracy and for tax, financing or investment purposes and it includes balance sheet (statement of financial position), income statement or statement of profit or loss, and cash flow statement.

Scharfman (2015) see financial statement as the disclosures pertaining to related-party transactions often start off with a general summary of the fees the investment manager receives and how often they receive them. This section then typically proceeds to include general disclaimer language, which,

unfortunately for investors, effectively gives the fund manager a great degree of fee flexibility. This language generally mimics similar language in the fund's offering memorandum, and reads something to the effect of "The investment manager, in its sole discretion, may reduce or waive the management fee with regards to certain limited partners."

Financial statement analysis is used by internal and external stakeholders to evaluate business performance and value financial accounting calls for all companies to create a statement of financial position, statement of profit or loss and statement of cash flow which form the basis of financial statement analysis. The analysis and interpretation of financial statement represent the last of the four major steps of accounting which are: Analysis of each transaction to determine the account to be debited and credited and the measurement and variation of each transaction to determine the amount involved; Recording of the information in journal, summarization in ledger's and preparation of a worksheet. Result in the presentation of information that aids the business manager, investors, and creditors.

Financial statements provide important information for a wide variety of decision, investors draw information from the statement of the firm in whose security they contemplate investor. Decision makers who contemplate acquiring total or partial ownership of an enterprise expect to secure return on their investments, such as dividends and increase in the value of their investment. Both dividend and increase in the value of shares of company depend on the future profitability of the business, so investors are interested in the future gain. Thus, financial statement quality is a type of information system that is utilized for communication and decision-making (Amahalu & Obi, 2020).

In basing investment decision on financial statements, sound knowledge of the investors is required in the analysis of financial statement or consultation of the service of a financial analyst in making an investment decision as investment decision that is made in isolation of financial statement is considered by Popoola, et al., (2014) as a lot like throwing darts in a dark room. The investment decision relates to the decision made by the investors or the top level management with respect to the amount of funds to be deployed in the investment opportunities. Simply, selecting the type of assets in which the funds will be invested by the firm is termed as the investment decision (Suraj, 2020). Investment decisions or analysis has to do with an efficient allocation of capital. It involves decision to commit the firm's funds to the long-term assets. Such decisions are of considerable importance to the firm since they tend to determine its value size by influencing its growths, profitability and risk. It can be seen that financial information is very essential and effective in making investment decisions in an organization be it public or private firms. In consequence the analysis of financial statement in investment decision in three selected banks in Nigeria focused on UBA, Zenith Bank and Access Bank Plc.

Statement of the Problem

Financial statements are one of the most significant statements to consider while making investment decisions, especially in the private sector. These declarations must be timely and of good quality; users within and outside of a company organization want high-quality financial statements in order to make well-informed investment decisions. This is to avoid financial reporting fraud and scandals that could

stymie investors' and other users' ability to make effective and informed investment decisions. Bad investment decisions can lead to poor results, which can be traced back to financial statement quality. Banks in the past (such as Oceanic Bank, Intercontinental Bank, Platinum Bank, and others) appear to have faced difficulties in surviving as a result of financial statement falsification and poor investment decisions, which are the result of the account statement's quality. Due to misstatements of earnings and equity, inaccurate fair value measures resulting from management bias, and its immoral approach, the rising use of accounting estimates in financial reporting has drawn a lot of criticism and concerns. Furthermore, goodwill impairment losses are thought to lack verifiability, have high measurement error, and the potential to be reported opportunistically. As a result, this will be at odds with the financial reporting objectives, which specify that financial data should be relevant for decision-making and so represent what it plans to reveal.

In the financial statements, the company manipulates figures by creative accounting, increasing or reducing numbers depending on what it wants at that moment. In the worst case, organizations might face with the failure and perhaps bankruptcy in the end. This paper aims to fill a knowledge gap by analysing the effect of financial statement on investment decision of deposit money banks in Nigeria

Objectives of the Study

The general objective is to analysis of financial statement on investment decision of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Specific objectives are to:

- i. examine how earnings per share influence return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- ii. determine how dividend per share influence return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- iii. assess how profit for the year influence return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. How does earnings per share influence return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria?
- ii. To what extent does dividend per share influence return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria?

iii. What is the influence profit for the year on return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

- H₀₁: Earnings per share have no significant influence on return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- H₀₂: Dividend per share has no significant influence on return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- H₀₃: Profit for the year has no significant influence on return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Framework

The relationship between dependent and independent variables were represented in the diagram as follows:

Fig. 1: Conceptual Model of Study, 2024

Financial Statement

Financial statement analysis consists of applying analysis tools and techniques to financial statements and other relevant data to show important relationships and obtain useful information. It can be defined as the process whereby information relating to the organization as a whole is reported to the outside world. They are reports on management and not to management. It deals with most external financial transactions of the organization. They are source documents of accounting information. They are referred to as the final accounts (Anaja & Emmanuel, 2015). It is a formal record of the financial activities and position of a business, person, or other entity. Relevant financial information is presented in a

structured manner and in a form easy to understand (IAS 2007). It describes certain attributes of a company that is considered to fairly represent its financial activities. It is also the means of communicating to interested parties the relevant information on resources, obligation and performances of the reporting entity.

Financial statements apart from stating the financial position of an organization provide other information such as the financial performance, value added, changes in equity and cash flows of the enterprise within a defined period of time to which it relates (Adetula, et al, 2016). This information is useful to a wide range of users making informed economic decisions. The quality of financial reporting is indispensable to the need of users who requires them for investment and other decision-making purposes (Eluyela, et al 2018). Financial reports can only be regarded as useful if it represents the “economic substance” of an organization in terms of relevance, reliability, comparability and aids interpretation simplicity (Iyoha & Faboyede, 2011; Eluyela et al, 2018). It is used to achieve two basic objectives: assessment of past performance and current position, and assessment future potential and related risks of a business. It also gives a well view of the stewardship and accountability of management (Agbaje & Oloruntoba, 2018). This also help the users to make economic decision may be to hold or sell their investment and may be to change the management.

In the view of Khanh (2010), financial statement fraud is the deliberate misrepresentation of the financial condition of an enterprise accomplished through the intentional misstatement or omission of amounts or disclosures in the financial statements in order to deceive financial statement users. Management fraud is usually seen as the same as the financial statement fraud due to the fact that the preparation and presentation of financial reporting information is the sole task of the management. Each time that there exit a financial statement fraud, the management is always aware of it.

Prior studies have identified that financial statement fraud can take several methods, such as reporting non existing income(fictitious revenue), preparing accounting information for different period, hiding indebtedness or expenditure,(incorrect expense recognition) wrong reporting, wrong assessment of

property values (incorrect asset valuation), (Everette, 2012; Sanyaolu, et al., 2020). Kwok (2005) reveals that judging from the angle of financial information, income, gains, or properties are usually overvalued, while loss of income, expenditure, debt are mostly under reported. Over reporting income, gains or properties make a firm look financially healthy. Under reporting income, over reporting expenditure is done by firms that try to evade tax. As much as financial statement fraud takes place, it becomes difficult to stop it along the line. If revenue is deliberately raised in a particular year, it would make the next year income to be smaller. Chief executives mostly continue this practice year after year, (Aburime, 2012). However, fictitious revenue has become one of the major aspects of manipulation in the financial statement. It is clear from available evidence that accounting for (fictitious revenue) income not earned, that is, non-existing income and bringing revenue from a different period to another are common in most financial statement, (Odunayo, 2014).

With particular reference to business organizations, parties interested in financial statement analysis are divided into two categories, namely: internal users and external users. The internal users include management and employees of an organization, while external include shareholders, investors, creditors, debenture/bond holders, financial analysis, etc (Mohammed, 2014).

Management and Employees: Financial statement analysis helps management and employees to know the operating results, financial position and future potentials of a business.

Shareholders/Owners: The analysis helps shareholders or owners of a business to ascertain the profitability of the operation of the business, as well as return on their investments.

Investors and Creditors: Financial statement analysis helps investors to know the profitability and return on investment in a business. In the other hand, it helps trade creditors and note holders to know the liquidity or the ability of a business to pay its debts when they fall due.

Debenture/bond holders: Those who lend money to the business would like to know the ability of the business to repay on maturity both the interests and the principal of the loans granted to it.

Financial analysis: Financial statement analysis enables financial analysis to offer professional advice to their clients on investments.

Earnings per share (EPS)

Earnings per shares is a part of a firm's income that is due to apiece remaining parts of mutual stock. Earnings per share also help people to have a better insight of dissimilar company's power to make money (Inyiama & Ozouli, 2014). Stockholders are the business's holders and equally such are permitted to a part of the incomes/paychecks. Earnings per share are the financial worth of the incomes portion of an enterprise would continuously be reflected in relative to additional corporations in command to make an extra knowledgeable or judicious venture conclusion. Stockholders typically checked their paychecks relation aimed at upcoming investors.

EPS measures are intended to represent the income earned (or loss incurred) by each ordinary share during a reporting period and therefore provide an indicator of reported performance for the period (Agha, 2014). Earnings per share is the ratio that indicates how much the ability to generate earnings per share Earnings per share is the ratio that describes the amount of rupiah gained for each share of common stock (Muhammad, et al, 2017). In general corporate management, common shareholders and prospective shareholders are keen to earnings per share. Earnings per share (EPS) are calculated as a company's profit divided by the outstanding shares of its common stock.

Dividend per Share

A dividend is the distribution of reward from a portion of the company's earnings and is paid to a class of its shareholders. A dividend is also a token reward paid to the shareholders for their investment in a company's equity, and it usually originates from the company's net profits (Chen, 2019). Dividends are decided and managed by the company's board of directors, though they must be approved by the shareholders through their voting rights. Dividends can be issued as cash payments, as shares of stock, or other property, though cash dividends are the most

common. Along with companies, various mutual funds and exchange traded funds (ETF) also pay dividends (Chen, 2019).

Dividend per share (DPS) is the sum of declared dividends issued by a company for every ordinary share outstanding. The figure is calculated by dividing the total dividends paid out by a business, including interim dividends, over a period of time, usually a year, by the number of outstanding ordinary shares issued (Boyle, 2021). Thus, dividend per share (DPS) is the sum of declared dividends issued by a company for every ordinary share outstanding. DPS is calculated by dividing the total dividends paid out by a business, including interim dividends, over a period of time, usually a year, by the number of outstanding ordinary shares issued. DPS is an important metric to investors because the amount a firm pays out in dividends directly translates to income for the shareholder (Boyle, 2021). A growing DPS over time can also be a sign that a company's management believes that its earnings growth can be sustained.

Profit for the Year

Profit means success for a business, and executives should be able to calculate that bottom line. Analysts use profit as a measure of a business's worth, helping investors make appropriate decisions. Profit for the year also referred to profit after tax is a financial measure that shows how well a company performed through its core operations, net of taxes. It is frequently used in economic value added (EVA) calculations and is a more accurate look at operating efficiency for leveraged companies. It can be fully retained by a company to be used in the business or distributed as dividends, if declared and to the share holders (Oliver, et al, 2017).

The profit for the year after-tax figure is considered the best measure of the ability of an entity to generate a return, since it incorporates both operating income and income from other sources, such as interest income. It is a measure of how competent a company is with regards to converting its revenue into profits, it is also used in margin analysis to compare companies within the same industry. According to Aldridge (2015), it helps investors determine how much a company actually earns and can also help determine whether a company needs to control its costs. The profit after-tax margin is closely watched by investors

to see if the income generating ability of a firm is changing over time (Oliver, et al, 2017). If so, this could be considered a valuation indicator that may result in a change in the stock price.

Investment Decision

The rate at which accounting scandals occurred recently in the international financial community has raised many criticisms about the financial reporting quality. The involvement of companies such as Enron, Worldcom, Marconi, Parmalat etc. in accounting frauds has weakened the investors' confidence in the quality of financial reporting (Akeju & Babatunde 2017). The provision of high quality financial reporting information is important because it influences the providers of capital and other stakeholders positively in making investment, financing and similar allocation decisions that enhance the overall market efficiency (International Accounting Standards Board, IASB, 2008).

Investment decision can be considered one of the most important decisions taken by investors, if not the most important one. The investment decision making process influence the investors affirmation in turbulent business environment and increase its market share (Martin, 2006). It concerns the issue of capital allocation for fixed assets or financial assets; central place returns to fixed assets, acquired as a result of capital investment. By this decision, financial resources at investors' disposal are allocated efficiently to acquire more market share. In addition, the available liquidities may be placed respecting the efficiency criteria on the capital market, to purchase financial assets (Zager & Zager, 2006). In any case of the chosen alternatives, the investment decision ought to be subordinated to achieve the investment objectives at long-term.

As postulated by Pandey (2005) investment decisions or analysis has to do with an efficient allocation of capital. It involves decision to commit the firm's funds to the long-term assets. Such decisions are of considerable importance to the firm since they tend to determine its value size by influencing its growths, profitability and risk. Some of the features of investment decisions are as follows; the exchange of

current funds for future benefits, the funds are invested in long-term assets, the benefits will occur to the firm over a series of years. The two importance aspects of investment decisions are; the evaluation of the prospective profitability of new investments, the measurement of a cut-off rate against that the prospective return of new investment could be compared (Anaja & Emmanuel, 2015).

To this end, the quality of investment decisions made relies on the value of the essential information that forms the source of that investment decision making (Popoola, et al, 2014). Of enormous value is the information published by financial statements, which generally provides a synopsis of all the other activities of the organization. To be of significance to investors and decision makers, published financial statement is generally suggested to be comprehensive both in content and quality (MacDonald & Koch, 2006). Sufficient guarantee has to be provided to make the information reliable and reduce uncertainty.

The major tool for these investment decisions is the ratio analysis (Abiahu & Amahalu, 2017). Ratio analysis is the judgmental process which aims at evaluating the current and past financial positions and the results of an entity, with the primary objectives of determining the best possible estimate about the future conditions and performances. It provides a quick diagnostic look at an entity's financial health and provokes subsequent financial and operational analysis (Kariuki & Jagongo, 2013).

Additionally, investment bankers also rely heavy on financial statement when determining the sustainability of a corporate business. For instance, a company cannot be bought or sold without determining an agreed-up on valuation. Therefore financial statements help bankers establish an appropriate price for transactions (Ekwe, 2013).

Return on equity (ROE)

Return on equity (ROE) is a measure of financial performance calculated by dividing net income by shareholders' equity [ROE=Net Income/Shareholder Equity]. ROE is considered a measure of the profitability of a corporation in relation to stockholders' equity. A percentage of net income over shareholder's equity is termed as return on equity (ROE). It measures the rate of return for ownership interest (shareholders)' equity of common stock owner

and tells how efficient a firm/company is at generating profits from each unit of shareholder equity, also known as net assets or assets minus liabilities bad (Ifeanyi & Francis, 2017). Return on Equity (ROE) is also profitability ratio that is used to measure the level of return the company or the effectiveness of the company in generating profits that are the rights of capital owners. ROE is calculated as net profit after tax divided by the total shareholder's equity. This ratio measures the shareholders rate of return on their investment in the company. Return on Equity (ROE), which constitutes as important indicator for stock holders and investor to determine company proficiency concerned with competence of earning after tax linked to dividend payout.

ROE is the best and most common measure of profitability, it does not consider factors such as timing of cash flows or turnovers (Angela, 2016). Increasing ROE is a positive indicator where as decreasing ROE usually creates problem (Mohsin & Midra, 2015). It is the most fundamental profitability ratio because stockholders are primarily interested in the relationship between net income and their investment in the company. It states net income as a percentage of equity. Return on equity which is a test of profitability based on the investments of the owners of the business. It measures the return which accrues to the shareholders after interest payments and taxes are deducted.

Theoretical Framework

Agency Theory

Agency theory was proponent by Jensen and Meckling in 1976. Agency theory is concerned with the conflicting interests of principals and agents. Jensen's and Meckling's (1976) model on agency costs and ownership structure holds a central role in the corporate governance literature. The theory abstracts from all other frictions away except the one between managers and owners, the empirical model we will build later on is significantly different. The theory, nevertheless, demonstrates well the fundamental conflict of interest between managers and owners.

The key insight of Jensen and Meckling (1976) was to model the relationship between owners and managers similar to one between a principal and an agent. The owners contract the managers to perform the

controlling tasks of a firm, and as both seek to maximize their own utility and are self-interested a conflict of interest arises. As the managers have the effective control of the firm, they have the incentive and the ability to consume benefits at the expense of the owners. Jensen and Meckling define the costs caused by the divergence of interests between owners and managers as agency costs consisting of 1) the monitoring expenditures by the principal, 2) bonding expenditures by the agent and 3) the residual loss, on which we will be especially focusing on.

The study submit that agency theory, despite all limitations, can be realize in this study by implementation of following: company is institution of people, with distinct members, and not only one owner; stakeholders have economic and noneconomic interests meaning that self-interest does not exclude interest for others; company is not only based on contractual agreements and company is also association of people; role of the company is not maximization of shareholders' wealth, yet self-actualization of all stakeholders.

Stakeholder Theory

Friedman (1970) the proponent of the theory that there is one and only one social responsibility of business to use its resources and engage in activities designed to increase its profits. By contrast, proponents of the stakeholder view of corporations assert that managers should pay attention not only to the profits of the shareholders but also to the welfare of their employees and consumers. This theory focuses on build-up on the concept of ethics in general. It defined ethics as the systematic reflection on what is moral. By this simple assent, morality is the whole of opinions, decisions and actions with which people express what they think is good or right. Ethical theory, according to Schofield (2006) sometimes focuses not on actions but majorly on consequences. The point in this theory is that, it is necessary to give the greatest happiness to the greatest number of people. The actions of the agents will be adjudged morally right in the process of running the corporations on behalf of the owners if the latter's interest is well represented whereas it will be adjudged wrong if their actions inflict pain on the interest of the principals.

The primary argument in favour of this approach is that shareholders are the "residual claimants" when

the company is solvent. It is believed that a company should be accountable for the benefit of the residual claimants, as shareholders being the equity investors are the "greatest stake in the outcome of the company. They may benefit from the company's surplus, but also bear a greater risk than other constituencies as their interests are not adequately protected by contractual means under most circumstances. Agency theory is relevant to the study, despite all limitations; the constituency in question can arguably be the shareholders or other stakeholder groups under the interpretation of different approaches. As a matter of fact, it is difficult to have a clear guiding principle to whose interests the company should serve even today, because of the ongoing developments of the society, insertion of more firm objectives.

In relation to the research objectives, this study adopted the agency theory. This is because it focuses on the board of directors as a mechanism which dominates the corporate governance literature. The agency theory, posit that the control function of an organization is primarily exercised by the board of directors. With regard to the board as a governance mechanism, the issues that appear most prominent in the literature are board composition (in particular board size, inside versus outside directors and the separation of CEO and chair positions) and the role and responsibilities of the board.

Empirical review

Ali-Momoh, et al (2022) analysed the effect of financial statements on financial decisions of listed deposit money bank in Nigeria during a 13-year period, from 2007 to 2020. The data was utilizing with aids of descriptive and inferential analytical techniques, followed by correlation analysis. Asset tangibility has a favourable but negligible influence on deposit money bank capital structure decisions in Nigeria. It was also revealed that asset tangibility has a negative and minor effect on deposit money institutions' liquidity decisions in Nigeria.

Olayinka (2022) looked into financial statement analysis as a tool for investment decisions and assessment of companies' performance using descriptive statistics between the years 2014 to 2019. The study showed that financial statements (FSs) is adequate for effective decision making and that firms should pay great attention to the use of FSA to properly equip themselves with this tool and also a

combination of different ratios should be used in analyzing a firm's financial performance.

Jaiyeoba and Ajayi (2022) investigated the effect of financial statements reporting quality on investment efficiency among some selected Deposit Money Banks listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange for a period of 10 years (2011-2020). The regression analysis of the least square was used. The findings revealed that statement of financial position (SOFP), income statement (IS) and cash flow statement (CFS) had significant positive effect on investment decision.

Ndum (2022) determined the effect of financial ratio analysis on performance of Food and Beverages companies in Nigeria, using market ratio, profitability ratio and return on assets. Ex-post facto research design was employed in the study. Simple linear regression was utilized. The data were obtained from the annual reports of the firms under study for a six (6) year period covering from 2015-2020. The result of the regression analysis reveals that market ratio and profitability ratio significantly affect return on assets of food and beverage companies in Nigeria.

Akani, and James (2022) examined the relationship between dividend policy decisions and profitability of quoted food and beverages manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2010-2019. The study employed panel data in the analysis while the fixed effects model was used as estimation technique at 5% level of significance. Fixed effects, random effects and pooled estimates were tested while the Hausman test was used to determine the best fit. The study found that dividend policy decisions affect profitability of quoted food and beverages manufacturing firms through return on equity.

Gandolph (2022) studied financial reporting and organization performance in Nigeria. The purpose of the research was to see how financial reporting affects organizational performance in Nigeria. The ex-post factor design method was employed for the course of this work. Data were extracted from ten Nigerian manufacturing companies. The study adopted inferential statistics for panel data analysis. The results demonstrated that financial reporting had a substantial impact on the performance of selected manufacturing enterprises in Nigeria.

Okunade (2021) investigated the effect of quality of financial reporting on value of shares traded in listed deposit money banks in Nigeria over a period of 10 years from 2010 to 2019. The study employed the ex post facto research design. The study found that quality of financial reporting has significant effect on value of shares traded.

Conteh and Akuntansi (2021) intended to investigate financial statements analysis and investment decision making in the Gambia between 2017 and 2018. The explanatory analysis was used. The findings show that financial statement analysis is critical in investment decision making.

Bayar, et al (2021) determined the factors affecting the quality of financial statements on investment decision making. A structured questionnaire was developed. Analysis of the data was carried out in accordance with conventional methods of factor analysis as the study utilized multiple regression method. It was discovered that growth has significant relationship quality of financial statement; business factor has significantly predicted quality of financial statement. That business factor has significant relationship with quality of financial statement.

Aigienohuwa and Uniamikogbo (2021) researched on profitability and timeliness of financial reports in Nigerian quoted companies from 2010 to 2019. The study employed an ex-post facto research design. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and simple regression. The result revealed that, there is a substantial association between profitability and financial report timeliness in Nigerian quoted companies.

Amahalu and Obi (2020) ascertained the effect of financial statement quality on investment decisions of quoted Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria from 2010-2019. Ex-Post Facto research design was employed while secondary data were collected from a sample of seven (7) DMBs. Inferential statistics using Pearson correlation and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression analysis were applied. Results of this study found that financial statement verifiability, financial statement timeliness, and financial statement understandability have a significant positive effect on Return on Equity of quoted Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

Abdulshakour (2020) aimed to know impact of financial statements on financial decision-making based on the descriptive and analytical approach; the findings showed that the financial statements are a key tool to know the financial position of the company, so they must be accurate and reliable before being published by management. The lack of credibility in the financial statements leads to mistrust in the company by investors and does not give them the possibility to diagnose and make sound decisions.

Berthilde and Rusibana (2020) analyzed the contribution of financial statements in investment decision making of banks in Rwanda taking the case of bank of Kigali from 2014 to 2018. Both a descriptive and a correlational research design were adopted and quantitative and qualitative methods were used. The finding revealed that holding independent variables constant to a constant zero, short term investment decision would be at 0.266 for common size analysis while the most significant p value was 0.008. Financial statements have significant and positive effect on investment decision making of banks in Rwanda.

Sanyaolu et al (2020) examines the effect of financial statement analysis on investment decision of Nigerian deposit money banks. An ex post facto research design was adopted. The hypotheses were tested using regression involving fixed-effect. It was found that profitability has a significant positive effect on investment decision; financial leverage has no significant positive effect on investment decision and that liquidity has no significant positive effect on investment decision.

Suraj (2020) examined the role of financial statement in investment decision making process based on analytical and descriptive research. The study found that financial statement plays a vital role in investment decision. It also found that financial statements are useful for forecasting company's performance.

Gap in Literature

Past studies reviewed for this study in line with financial statement on investment decision firms did not give adequate information in terms of accounting information from financial statement in order to create enabling environment for profitability and create more wealth for shareholders. The empirical studies by different authors did not have a detailed explanation

on the analysis of financial statement on investment decision in money deposit banks in Nigeria using earnings per share, dividend per share, profit for the year and return on equity as yardsticks in the banking industry in Nigeria was found missing in the past literatures reviewed. It failed in expending to recent period via 2012 to 2022 was found missing in the past literatures reviewed as the study used three selected banks in Nigeria, UBA, Zenith Bank and Access Bank Plc. This shows a gap in literature hence, justifying the conduct of this paper.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopts the *ex-post facto* design method. This is the type of research involving events that have already taken place. Accordingly, this research design will help in analysing financial statement on investment decision in Nigerian banks.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprises entire money deposit banks listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group and published in the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGXgroup) website. They are as follows: First Bank of Nigeria, Zenith Bank, Guaranty Trust Bank, Fidelity Bank, Access Bank, Diamond Bank, Eco Bank, United Bank for Africa, Skye Bank, Stanbic IBTC Bank, First City Monument Bank, Union Bank of Nigeria, Citi Bank, Heritage Bank, Keystone Bank, Stanbic IBTC, Standard Chartered Bank, Sterling Bank, Unity Bank and Wema Bank all located in Lagos for the period 2012-2022.

Sources of Data

The study made use of secondary data. The secondary data were obtained from the annual reports and accounts of the sampling money deposit banks in Nigeria covering a period of 11 years (2012-2022). Secondary data is considered appropriate given the fact that this data had been used in prior studies and is basically attempting to establish effect or lack of it under the study variables.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Purposive sampling technique was adapted to select banks whose financial statements is available with the Nigeria Stock Exchange from 2012-2022. The decision to use this time frame was made since the

banks' websites made it simple to retrieve data. However, the sample size was restricted three (3) banks: UBA, Zenith Bank and Access Bank Plc. The choice of these banks is because they have grown and performed consistently. These banks are recognition as Nigeria's top corporate governance banks.

$U_t =$ stochastic error associated with the models

Data Analysis Techniques

The panel data regression was used to analysis financial statement and investment decision covering 2012 to 2022 using the using E-views 10. Multiple regressions were used to test the combined effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The diagnostic test was also included. Thus, the procedure for data analysis includes descriptive and inferential statistics..

Model Specification

Panel data regression technique was used to evaluate the relationship between variables. Thus, based on the above theoretical underpinnings, the model is specified as:

$$\text{Model 1: ROA} = f(\text{EPS}) - - - (1)$$

$$\text{ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EPS} + U_t$$

$$\text{Model 2: ROA} = f(\text{DPS}) - - - (2)$$

$$\text{ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{DPS} + U_t$$

$$\text{Model 3: ROA} = f(\text{PY}) - - - (3)$$

$$\text{ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{PY} + U_t$$

Main Model/General Function

$$\text{ROA} = f(\text{EPS}, \text{DPS}, \text{PY})$$

$$\text{ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EPS} + \beta_2 \text{DPS} + \beta_3 \text{PY} + U_t - (4)$$

Where,

ROA= Return on Assets at time t, (dependent variable)

EPS= earnings per share at time t, (independent variable)

DPS= dividend per share at time t, (independent variable)

PY= profit for the year at time t, (independent variable)

$\beta_0 =$ Constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 =$ Regression coefficients or coefficients of the independent Variables.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Presentation of Data

Table 1: Showing return on equity (ROE), earnings per share (EPS), dividend per share (DPS), log of profit for the year (LPY)

BANKS	YEAR	ROE	EPS	DPS	LPY
UBA	2012	0.38	1.44	0.50	10.83780
	2013	0.37	1.41	0.50	10.92684
	2014	0.39	1.22	0.10	10.59871
	2015	0.35	1.36	0.40	10.77147
	2016	0.35	1.31	0.55	10.76935
	2017	0.36	1.20	0.65	10.65580
	2018	0.35	1.20	0.85	10.62247
	2019	0.60	1.83	1.00	11.04691
	2020	0.49	1.66	0.52	10.94924
	2021	0.51	1.72	1.00	10.97967
2022	0.22	3.91	1.60	11.80332	
Zenith Bank	2012	0.10	3.05	1.60	11.51971
	2013	0.10	2.66	1.75	11.46497
	2014	0.12	2.95	1.75	11.50746
	2015	0.10	3.15	2.00	11.56801
	2016	0.10	4.12	1.80	11.77261
	2017	0.12	5.66	2.02	12.06561
	2018	0.12	5.27	2.60	12.17264
	2019	0.10	5.67	2.80	12.24934
	2020	0.10	6.30	2.80	12.34829
	2021	0.10	7.43	3.00	12.40721
2022	0.10	6.88	3.00	12.28182	
Access Bank	2012	0.22	1.57	0.06	8.565602
	2013	0.21	1.14	0.06	10.48612
	2014	0.25	1.74	0.06	10.17393
	2015	0.31	2.37	0.05	10.59516
	2016	0.34	2.21	0.06	11.09541
	2017	0.28	2.18	0.65	10.84613
	2018	0.44	3.30	0.50	11.20635
	2019	0.44	1.73	0.65	11.15789
	2020	0.42	3.00	0.80	11.29027
	2021	0.64	3.13	1.00	11.62022
2022	0.16	4.69	1.33	12.02371	

Source: Researcher's Study, 2024

Analysis of Data

Table 2: Descriptive statistics results

	ROE	EPS	DPS	LPY
Mean	0.280000	2.983636	1.151818	11.22364
Median	0.280000	2.370000	0.850000	11.15789
Maximum	0.640000	7.430000	3.000000	12.40721
Minimum	0.100000	1.140000	0.050000	8.565602
Std. Dev.	0.159980	1.815416	0.937642	0.778401
Skewness	0.427503	0.996250	0.649608	-0.925968
Kurtosis	2.203132	2.875436	2.244813	5.268706
Jarque-Bera	1.878299	5.480160	3.105124	11.79295
Probability	0.390960	0.064565	0.211705	0.002749
Sum	9.240000	98.46000	38.01000	370.3800
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.819000	105.4636	28.13349	19.38904
Observations	33	33	33	33

Source: e-view output, 2024

In table 2 all the variables summary statistics under study in their raw form have been shown. Particularly, return on equity (ROE), earnings per share (EPS), dividend per share (DPS), log of profit for the year (LPY) stood at about ₦0.280000m, ₦2.983636m, ₦1.151818m and ₦11.22364m, showing the 11 years of UBA, Zenith and Access bank covering a period of 2012 to 2022 under study average value, and equally, it shows their various minimum and maximum values as well as their changes over the years. On the other hand, the sum of squares dev. above 0.819000, 105.4636, 28.13349 and 19.38904 respectively is a measure of deviation from the mean. Illustrating the spread in the data series was the standard deviation value, 0.159980, 1.815416, 0.937642 and 0.778401 respectively; therefore shows the lower the value, the lower the deviation of the series from the mean and the higher the value, the higher the deviation of the series from its mean. The variables of standard deviation are all lesser than their mean showing lower growth.

The table 2 as well shows the true nature of the data series as seen in the skewness, kurtosis and Jarque-

Berra test statistics of all variables. It is said that a probability distribution that is perfectly symmetric around the mean will have zero skewness. All the series are normally distributed due to the normality of the series of return on equity (ROE), earnings per share (EPS), dividend per share (DPS), log of profit for the year (LPY) respectively and since the probability value of Jarque-berra statistics with 1.878299, 5.480160, 3.105124 and 11.79295 of all the series are shown to be more than the acceptable 0.05. Their respective p-value 0.390960, 0.064565, 0.211705 and 0.002749 for ROE, EPS, DPS and LPY respectively are more than 0.05 assumed levels significance. Based on the majority of probability values for Jarque Berra statistics in the descriptive table 2 are all the series of normally distributed. Thus, the regression model is estimated using the transformed series as one of the assumption of ordinary least square regression is normality of series which have been met.

Table 3: Panel Pooled OLS (POLS) results
Dependent Variable: ROE

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EPS	-0.033184	0.026477	-1.253307	0.2201
DPS	-0.125337	0.054489	-2.300222	0.0288
LPY	0.106183	0.051971	2.043119	0.0502
C	-0.668389	0.535938	-1.247139	0.2223

Source: e-view output, 2024

In table 3 above, EPS is statistically insignificant since its p-values of 0.22 > 0.05 level of significance. Similarly, the coefficient of DPS and LPY are positive with 0.029 and 0.05 ≤ 0.05 meaning that they statistically significant. The coefficient of LPY is 0.106183 is positive meaning that a unit increase in LPY will cause a unit increase on ROE. On the other hand, the coefficient EPS and DPS are negative with -0.033184 and -0.125337 respectively meaning that a unit decrease in DPS and LPY will result in a unit decrease in ROE.

Fig. 1: Normality Test Results

Source: e-view output, 2024

The Jarque-Bera statistics 4.024352 of the series is shown to be greater than the acceptable 0.05, with respective p-value 0.099045 higher than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the data is normally distributed.

Table 4: Results of multicollinearity test Variance Inflation Factors

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
EPS	0.000701	19.34570	5.110473
DPS	0.002969	14.75882	5.773792
LPY	0.002701	779.7288	3.619910
C	0.287230	655.1771	NA

Source: e-view output, 2024

The results of multicollinearity show that the variance inflation factors (VIF) for EPS, DPS, and LPY of 5.110473, 5.773792 and 3.619910 respectively are all less than 10, implying that multicollinearity does not exist in the model.

Table 5: Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.697423	Prob. F(3,29)	0.5612
Obs*R-squared	2.220644	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.5279
Scaled explained SS	2.324465	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.5079

Source: e-view output, 2024

The above result shows that the probability chi-square $0.5279 > 0.05$ level of significance. It means that the null hypothesis is correct indicating there is no Heteroscedasticity in the data.

Table 6: Results of test of Autocorrelation using Durbin-Watson stat

R-squared	0.067292	Mean dependent var	0.012714
Adjusted R-squared	-0.029195	S.D. dependent var	0.021257
S.E. of regression	0.021565	Akaike info criterion	-4.722265
Sum squared resid	0.013487	Schwarz criterion	-4.540870
Log likelihood	81.91737	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-4.661231
F-statistic	0.697423	Durbin-Watson stat	1.898925
Prob(F-statistic)	0.561198		

Source: e-view output, 2024

The result in table 6 shows that the Durbin-Watson stat. in the above table 6 is 1.898925 and less than 2, it shows there is a positive Autocorrelation.

Table 7: Result of multiple regression analysis Dependent Variable: ROE

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EPS	-0.033184	0.026477	-1.253307	0.2201
DPS	-0.125337	0.054489	-2.300222	0.0288
LPY	0.106183	0.051971	2.043119	0.0502
C	-0.668389	0.535938	-1.247139	0.2223

R-squared	0.487730	Mean dependent var	0.280000
Adjusted R-squared	0.434737	S.D. dependent var	0.159980
S.E. of regression	0.120280	Akaike info criterion	-1.284782
Sum squared resid	0.419549	Schwarz criterion	-1.103387
Log likelihood	25.19890	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-1.223748
F-statistic	9.203606	Durbin-Watson stat	1.169803
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000195		

Source: e-view output, 2024

The results of the correlation analysis presented in table 7 above shows that R^2 , the multiple coefficient of determination of the variables stood at 0.487730 indicating that about 48.77% of the total variation in ROE is explained by variations in the independent variables captured in the study. The adjusted R^2 being 0.434737 also indicates that the independent variables

will still explain 43.48% of the variations in ROE even if other variables were added to the study. More so, the assumption of no auto correlation of the error terms is also a requirement of linear regression. Norusis (1995) is of the opinion that Durbin-Watson can be used to test the independence of error terms. He added that the general rule of thumb is that if the Durbin-Watson value is between 1.5 and 2.5, the assumption of independence of the terms is not violated. The Durbin Watson coefficient stood at 1.169803 as shown in Table 7 which falls within the benchmark. This indicates the absence of harmful serial correlation. The F-statistic which measures the adequacy and fitness of the model used in the study stood at 9.203606 with a p-value of 0.000195 which is significant at 5%; this shows that the model is fit for the data. Thus, the model is considered fit and any conclusion made from it.

H₀₁: Earnings per share have no significant influence on return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Earnings per share (EPS) are found to be negatively related to the investment decision (return on equity) of UBA, Zenith Bank and Access Bank Plc. It has a beta coefficient of -0.033184. The independent variable ROE appears negative coefficient. It means that for every decrease in one unit of the variable, the dependent variable ROE will decrease by the coefficient values of the variable. Hence, if an additional one Naira is expended on EPS, this could leads to a fall in ROE by 0.033184. However, the value of the (p-value) 0.2201 is more than 0.05 level of significant indicates that Earnings per share actually have an insignificant effect on return on equity. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and an alternative hypothesis is rejected. We therefore, conclude that Earnings per share has no significant effect on return on equity of UBA, Zenith Bank and Access Bank Plc.

H₀₂: Dividend per share has no significant influence on return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Dividend per share (DPS) is found to be negatively related to the investment decision (return on equity) of UBA, Zenith Bank and Access Bank Plc. It has a beta coefficient of -0.125337. The independent variable ROE appears negative coefficient. It means that for

every decrease in one unit of the variable, the dependent variable ROE will decrease by the coefficient values of the variable. Hence, if an additional one Naira is expended on EPS, this could leads to a fall in ROE by 0.125337. However, the value of the (p-value) 0.0288 is less than 0.05 level of significant indicates that Dividend per share (DPS) actually have an insignificant effect on return on equity. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and an alternative hypothesis is accepted. We therefore, conclude that Dividend per share has significant effect on return on equity of UBA, Zenith Bank and Access Bank Plc.

H₀₃: Profit for the year has no significant influence on return on equity in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Profit for the year (PY) is found to be positively related to the investment decision (return on equity) of UBA, Zenith Bank and Access Bank Plc. It has a beta coefficient of 0.106183. The independent variable ROE appears positive coefficient. It means that for every decrease in one unit of the variable, the dependent variable ROE will decrease by the coefficient values of the variable. Hence, if an additional one Naira is expended on PY, this could leads to an increase in ROE by 0.106183. However, the value of the (p-value) 0.0502 is more than 0.05 level of significant indicates that Profit for the year actually have an insignificant effect on return on equity. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and an alternative hypothesis is rejected. We therefore, conclude that Profit for the year has no significant effect on return on equity of UBA, Zenith Bank and Access Bank Plc.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Financial statements contain lots of information summarized in figures. Viewed on the surface, they do not provide enough information about the viability of the reporting entity. Thus, they need to be analyzed by means of financial ratios to unravel the mass of truth hidden in them, and to enhance decision-making. Ratio analysis helps to reveal, compare and interpret salient features of financial statements. They help to identify the strengths and weaknesses of a business. In this study, 'the role of analysis of financial statement in investment decision in Nigeria,' claims that the accounting information in the financial statement

plays an important role in reflecting in the profit of listed Banks in Nigeria. The study therefore concludes that: earnings per share have no significant influence on return on equity, dividend per share has significant influence on return on equity and that profit for the year has no significant influence on return on equity in UBA, Zenith Bank and Access Bank Plc.

Recommendations

- i. The management of money deposit banks in Nigeria should assign more important to earnings per share since it shows how much a business is winning or earnings. High earnings show a higher productivity of focused tasks. This would as well help to determine whether the banks have performed up to the standard required by the industry.
- ii. It also recommended that the shareholders in the deposit money banks should be guided by industry financial ratios, especially the profitability measures of dividend pay-out ratio, as they are critical factors in predicting share price behavior. The managers of the firms should also formulate policies that will ensure efficiency and effectiveness of the firm's assets to bring about profitability for the firm.
- iii. Finally, the management of UBA, Zenith Bank and Access Bank Plc and other banks in Nigeria should improve on their wealth creation by cutting unnecessary cost and they should applied return on profit margin ratios to improve the financial situation and operational efficiency of the companies. This will go a long way to increase their total value of shares of stock.

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